

AN AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF INDRALUPTA (ALOPACIA AREATA)- A SINGLE CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Hair disorders cause negative effect on one's quality of life. Alopecia areata, is one such autoimmune disease characterised by nonscarring patchy hair loss. It can be correlated with *Indralupta* in Ayurveda, explained under the category of *Kshudra roga* and *Shirakapala roga*. There are many kinds of treatment modalities explained in the contemporary sciences. But, due to its side effects and limitations, there is a need for effective and harmless treatment. Ayurveda has a great potential in treating autoimmune disorders by means of *Shodhana* and *Shamana Chikitsa*. A female patient of patchy hair loss noticed 15 days ago was treated with treatment modalities like *Nasya* and *Pracchanna karma* along with internal medications. There was significant reduction in her symptoms. Thus, the positive result of the Ayurvedic management is presented as a case study in this article.

KEYWORDS: Alopecia areata, *Indralupta*, *Nasya*, *Pracchanna*, *Ichhabhedi Rasa*.

INTRODUCTION

Alopecia areata (AA)^[1] is a common disease of autoimmune nature which presents as nonscarring hair loss. It accounts for almost 25% of all causes of alopecia. The hair loss may involve any hair bearing area with no inflammatory signs. The severity varies from small patches of hair loss to complete alopecia. The prevalence of AA is variable from 0.1% to 0.2% and having a lifetime risk of 1.7%.⁵ Males and females can be equally affected,

however, male predominance have been reported in some studies. It may present at any age with a peak age of onset between 2nd and 4th decade.

It typically presents with sharply demarcated round patches of hair loss with characteristic exclamation point hairs observed on periphery of the patches. Other than the genetic disposition, infectious pathogens like virus or bacteria, emotional and physical stress, vaccines and drugs may also be triggering factors.

In Ayurveda, there is a brief explanation about the concept of *Indralupta*. It is a type of *Kapalagata Roga* according to Acharya Vagbhata^[2] and Acharya Sushruta has mentioned it under *Kshudrarogas*.^[3] It occurs when *Pitta* along with *Vata* affecting the hair follicles to become thin and fall, later on, due to vitiation of *Kapha* and *Rakta* it blocks the regrowth of hairs.

The main treatment in contemporary science is corticosteroids which is having harmful side effects and not advisable for long term use. Ayurveda offers different preventive and curative treatment modalities for its management. Both *Shodhana* and *Shamana* treatment are prescribed for *Indralupta*. Here a case of female patient suffering from Alopecia areata was successfully treated with line of management as per Ayurveda.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This is a case report of 39 years old female patient who approached outpatient department of Shalakya Tantra, GAMC, Bengaluru.

CASE REPORT

Chief Complaints With Duration

Generalized, excessive hair fall since 1 month.

Patchy hair loss over the scalp noticed 15 days ago.

History Of Present Illness

A 39-year-old female patient was apparently healthy 1 month ago. She gradually started developing complaints of generalised hair fall since 1 month. A week ago, she noticed patchy hair loss in 3 areas; one located in the right postauricular region, one at the vertex of the scalp and one along the frontal scalp near the hairline. The exact onset of these patches is uncertain. Gradually the severity of hair fall and diameter of patches increased, hence patient approached our hospital.

History Of Past Illness

No history of systemic diseases like asthma, hypertension, diabetes.

No history of autoimmune diseases like vitiligo, Hashimoto's thyroiditis, lupus erythematosus; major psychological disorders etc.

Family History

Nothing significant.

Personal History

Appetite- Good

Bowel- Regular, once a day

Micturition- 4-5 times a day

Sleep- sound

Diet- mixed, more of red meat and fish.

Vihara- Chinta, Krodha

Asta Sthana Pariksha

Nadi – Vatakaphaja, Mutra- Prakrita, Mala- Prakrita, Jihwa- Lipta, Shabda and Sparsha – Prakrita, Drik- Prakrita and Akriti-Sthula.

General And Systemic Examination

No abnormality detected.

Local Examination

Table 1: Examination of scalp.

Parameters	Findings
Number of patches	3
Site of hair loss scalp	One located in the right postauricular region, one at the vertex of the scalp and one along the frontal scalp near the hairline.
Size of the patch	4x3 cm, 1.5x1.5cm, 2x1cm respectively
The skin on the patch	Normal, no scar or inflammation present
Shape	Circular
Discharge	Absent
Sensation	Normal
Itching	Absent
Scales	Absent

Diagnostic Assessment

Thyroid dysfunction and anaemia were ruled out through blood investigations. Scalp colour was normal with no signs of vitiligo, fungal infection, or dandruff. The patient was clinically diagnosed as a case of *Indralupta*.

Table 02: Blood Parameters.

Blood Parameters	Observed value	Normal range
Haemoglobin (g%)	12	12-15
RBC (million/cu mm)	4.4	4.1-5.1
WBC (/cu mm)	5600	4000-10000
ESR (mm/hr)	14	0-15
T3	130	100-200
T4	7.0	5.0-12.0
TSH	3.6	0.5-5
Serum Calcium (mg/dl)	10.43	8.8-10.6
Vit D 25- hydroxy (ng/mL)	20.32	30-100, deficient-<20
Vit B12 (pg/ml)	281.24	187.00-883.00

Treatment Protocol- Table 03, 04 And 05

<i>Shodhana Chikitsa</i>	Medicine Used	Duration
<i>Prachhanna Karma</i>	<i>Gharshana With Trikatu Churna, Prachhanna Followed By Lepa Of Icchabhedi Rasa</i>	7 Sittings Once In 3 Days
<i>Nasya</i>	<i>Anu Taila</i>	7 Days

Internal Medicine	Dose	Duration
<i>Hingwashtaka Churna</i>	1 Tsp Bd With First Morsel Of Food With Ghee	7 Days
<i>Arogyavardhini Vati</i>	1-0-1 A/F	30 Days
<i>Krimikuthara Rasa</i>	1-0-1 A/F	30 Days
<i>Aragwadhadi Kashaya</i>	20ml Bd B/F	30 Days
<i>Indukanta Ghrita</i>	5g Daily Empty Stomach In The Morning	30 Days
<i>Narasimha Rasayana</i>	5g Daily Empty Stomach In The Morning	30 Days

Provided Treatment And Follow Up.

Days	Findings
1 st day	Investigations done and <i>Prachhanna</i> followed by <i>lepa</i> of <i>Icchabhedi Rasa</i> started.
20 th day	<i>Nasya</i> with <i>Anutaila</i> was started.
27 th day	Started with internal medications for a month.
57 th day	Prescribed <i>Narasimha Rasayana</i> for a month.

OBSERVATION AND RESULTS

After 7 sittings of *Prachhanna* and *Lepa* partial regrowth of hair was observed in the patches. After a sitting of *Nasya*, generalised hair fall was slightly reduced. After 2 months of internal medications, significant hair growth was visible in all three patches, hair fall was comparatively reduced. (Figure 1-9).

Fig.1: Patch located in the vertex of the scalp, before treatment

Fig.2: After 1 month (completion of *Prachhanna* and *Nasya*)

Fig.3: After 2 months of internal medications.

Fig.4: Patch located in the frontal scalp near the hairline, before treatment

Fig.5: After 1 month (completion of *Prachhanna* and *Nasya*)

Fig.6: After 2 months of internal medications.

Fig.7: Patch located in the right postauricular region, before treatment

Fig.8: After 1 month (completion of *Prachhanna* and *Nasya*)

Fig.9: After 2 months of internal medications.

DISCUSSION

According to Ayurveda, *Indralupta* is one of the *Urdhwajatrugata Vyadhi* characterized by the patchy hair loss. *Nidana* like *Chinta*, *Krodha* and *Mithyahara sevana* which was seen in the patient could have collectively increased the *Pitta* and *Vata Dosha* due to which the *Sneha* and the *Pichchhilatva* of the *Kapha Dosha* are dried up within the pores of the skin of the scalp thus, obstructing the growth of new hairs, causing *Indralupta*. Thus *Vata*, *Pitta* and *Kapha Dosha* and *Rakta Dushya* are the main internal causative factors of *Indralupta*.^[4]

The *Shodhana Chikitsa* has been described as the first line of treatment. *Pracchanna*^[5] is one among the *Shastrakruta Raktamokshana* which acts as a local *Shodhana* procedure. It removes the vitiated *Rakta* locally from the scalp. *Ichhabhedi rasa*,^[6] a classical ayurvedic preparation which contains *Jayapala*, with Phorbol esters present in it. These have skin irritant effect and it regulates cell growth and cell differentiation thus favors the re growth of hair. After *Prachhanna*, *Marsha Nasya* is done with *Anutaila* which by its *Sukshmasrotogami* and *Vatapittahara karma*, helps in *Samprapti Vighatana* and helps in new hair growth.

After *Shodhana*, there can be *Vataprakopa* and *Dhatukshaya* may persist. *Indukanta Ghrita* being *Vatashamaka*, *Balya* and *Brimhana*, nourishes *Rasadhatu* and promotes hair regrowth. Hence it is used as *Shamana Snehapana* after these procedures. *Hingwastaka churna* was given at first for the *Pachana* of *Amadosha* prior to *Snehapana*.

Since *Krimi* is one of the *Nidana* for *Shiroroga*, *Krimikuthara Rasa* was given to address the *Krimi* and also to prevent any secondary infections arising from open wounds caused post *Pracchanna Karma*.^[7] *Arogyavardhini Vati* acts as antioxidant and hepatoprotective, improves the *Rasa-Rakta* formation thereby promoting hair nourishment. *Aragwadhadi Kashaya* has *Vishahara*, *Kushta* and *Pitta-Kaphahara dravyas* with mild laxative action, thus it aids in elimination of accumulated toxins and works as the principles of detoxification. *Narasimha Rasayana* is a special type of *Rasayana Yoga* explained in *Astanga Hridaya*. Its main indication is premature greying of hair and hair loss and has *Vata-Pittahara* property.^[8]

CONCLUSION

From the above case discussion, it can be concluded that the patient suffering from *Indralupta* underwent a successful treatment using *Shodhana* and *Shamana* therapy. Along with the conservative treatment, *Nidana Parivarjana*, *Pathya* and *Apathya* was also considered and kept in mind for the better outcome of the full procedure. In order to confirm the efficacy of

this treatment protocol statistically, it is essential to conduct a thorough clinical evaluation involving a large population of patients.

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